

Influence of Learning Environment and Instructional Resources on Academic Performance of Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the influence of learning environment and instructional resource on academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions.

Four research questions were raised to guide the investigation. The descriptive survey was used as the design of the study. Population of the study comprised 908 business Education students from Delta State tertiary institutions in the 2024/2025 academic session. The sample size of 227 was arrived at using the simple random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection from the respondents. Mean and Standard Deviation was used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that physical space influence business education students' academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent. Also, the finding also showed that instructional resources significantly influence business education students' academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions. The study concluded that instructional resources are a better predictor of Business Education students' academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions than learning environment. The study recommended amongst others that management of Delta State tertiary institutions should ensure that the institutions does not lack instructional resource since it enhance students' academic performance.

KEYWORDS: Learning Environment, Instructional Resources, Academic Performance, Business Education, Students

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INTRODUCTION

The foundation of any country's growth is education. This is the rationale behind a government's significant investment in its citizens' education. A subset of education, secondary education is crucial to the development of human capital. For admittance to their various programs, postsecondary schools draw their key students from this particular supply base. Therefore, it assumes that the achievement of secondary education's objectives depends on the provision of high-quality instruction. However, the learning environment must adopt an appropriate perspective for the advancement of the overall educational objectives in order to achieve these aims. The learning environment is among the simplest to comprehend.

The effect is evident in the architecture, lighting, flooring, furniture, and other elements. It can also include interior color schemes, space accessibility, and cleanliness. Students' emotional, cognitive, and social functioning can be impacted by the school's physical learning environment, which can communicate non-verbally by either welcoming or discouraging and valuing or degrading them (Hussain, 2021). Students' behavior and academic performance are greatly impacted by classroom environmental conditions, according to several studies. Low student performance is associated with inadequate illumination, poor air quality, and inadequate heating (Cheryan et al., 2014). As a result, it is essential to assess how space is used in order to remove any negative factors. The school learning environment should be well structured, organized, studied and well managed for the attainment of the secondary school education goals and to enhance students' academic performance.

The government, ministry of education, parents, teachers, and even students themselves have been deeply concerned about the issue of Nigerian students' poor academic performance. The quality of education depends not only on the teachers' performance of their duties but also on the efficient coordination of the school learning environment (Okoro, 2020). Teachers, students, and the

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learning process are all impacted by the physical features of the school. Poor lighting, noise, excessive carbon dioxide levels in the classroom, and unpredictable temperatures make teaching and learning challenging. It has been noted that inadequate upkeep and inefficient ventilation systems cause ill health in both instructors and pupils, which results in subpar work and increased absenteeism.

These elements may have a negative impact on students' behavior, increase instructor annoyance, and cause pupils to have a negative attitude about learning. Effective secondary education requires a setting that is favorable to learning, giving students time and space to engage with the teaching and learning process. Effective classroom management, participatory learning, and an overall demonstration of an innovative atmosphere may all contribute to the creation and maintenance of an engaging learning environment (Okoro, 2021). A well-planned, structured, and organized space where instruction takes place is called a school learning environment. The location or environment might be a classroom, a library, a school laboratory where students do experiments and practical work, or a technical workshop, among other places. According to Narad and Abdullah (2016), academic performance is defined as the information gained that is evaluated by a teacher using grades or educational goals that students and instructors establish to be accomplished within a specific time period. Academic performance, then, is the result of education; it is the degree to which an institution has fulfilled its educational objectives. As a result, there are elements influencing how well students do academically in the classroom.

According to Danesy and Okediran (2002), cited by Kolo and Baba (2020), a learning environment that is not free of obstacles, noise, gas, smoke, pollution, and other things can be considered a health hazard. This can impair students' ability to concentrate in the classroom, which in turn affects their academic performance. Students' academic achievement has always been at risk from markets and garages close to schools. These sources of pollution and noise have long put students' lives and focus at risk. Environmental risks in learning environments have a detrimental effect on students' academic performance and health, according to several studies conducted by different authors. In educational settings, noise pollution that is higher than the WHO's recommended 35 dB for schools is a major problem (Agaja & Akande, 2024). The unfortunate issue of the terrible learning environment and poor academic performance of secondary school students in the area under review and Nigeria at large has been of much concern to the all stakeholders. The quality of education not only depends on the teachers as reflected in the discharge of their duties, but also in the effective coordination of the learning environment (Okoro, 2021).

For every nation, including Nigeria, to grow effectively, education is crucial. Nigeria's adoption of western education is heavily influenced by individualism, socioeconomics, and globalization, all of which are intended to promote national growth and integration. According to Okoro (2021), pupils' consistently low academic performance is one of the main barriers to the growth of secondary schools in Nigeria. People believe that Nigeria's educational standards are declining because of this reality. Recent records of poor academic performance have shown that many pupils do not meet the qualifications needed to be admitted to postsecondary educational institutions. According to Okoro (2021), a variety of reasons are thought to have contributed to the pupils' subpar academic performance in school. The authors emphasize that a variety of factors, such as poor study habits and a lack of resources, a poor school learning environment, indiscipline, inadequate facilities, teachers' ineffectiveness, the teaching method, and the kind of learning environment available for both students and teachers, may contribute to students' low academic achievement. According to the authors, the kind of learning environment may be reflected in the low performance of elementary school students.

The physical, social, and psychological setting in which learning occurs is referred to as a learning environment. Physical spaces like classrooms, libraries, and online platforms; social interactions like student-teacher and peer relationships; instructional resources like materials, tools, and technology; organizational structure like schedules, policies, and procedures; and psychological elements like motivation, engagement, and emotional support are all included in the term "learning environment." As a result, a well-designed learning environment promotes student achievement and learner engagement. Put differently, the teaching and learning of business education at the postsecondary level may be impacted by the learning environment. This is due to the fact that the phrase describes the various physical settings, situations, and cultural contexts in which pupils acquire knowledge.

A learning environment encompasses learning resources and technology which are means of teaching, modes of learning, and connections to societal and global contexts. The term also includes human behavioural and cultural dimensions, including the vital role of emotion in learning and it requires us to examine and sometimes rethink the roles of teachers and students. By implication, the learning environment is the combination of living things and the physical environment. According to Clint (2021), there are four different types of learning environments. He says it can be students or learner-centered, knowledge-centered, assessment-centered, and community-centered. The feature of each is that a learner-centered environment pays close attention to the needs of the students, a knowledge-centered environment focuses on helping students to learn information with deep understanding so students can use it in new situations and contexts, and assessment-centered environment stresses the importance of feedback to learners. While the community-centered learning environment focuses on collaborative and inclusive approaches, prioritizing the needs and experiences of the community. Key aspects include collaboration where students, teachers, and community members work together, sharing knowledge and expertise.

Lee (2018) relates the idea of a learning environment to classroom management. According to this, classroom setup is an important component in a learning environment. Further, it is an essential piece of classroom management to support both teaching and learning. In his opinion, the physical atmosphere of the classroom can help prevent behaviour issues as well as promote

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improved learning. Therefore, the structuring of the learning environment is essential for teachers and students. He believes that the physical arrangement of the classroom can affect both students' and teachers' behaviour as well. A structured classroom management plan can improve learning and behaviour. He suggested that to create an inviting, safe, supportive learning environment, teachers are to use classroom management to encourage high-performing students through the use of students-centered, knowledge-centered, and assessment-centered learning environments respectively.

The impact of any of the identified learning environments on learners' learning outcomes and performance is traced in the study by Hendrix (2019) who found that the learning environment plays a crucial role in students' success. He discovered that several factors can affect the learning ability of a majority of learners due to a negative learning environment. Some of these factors include bad seating arrangement in the class, poor lighting system, uncontrollable noise, inappropriate use of colour; whereas he noticed that students who study in a positive and well-organized classroom learning environment get more motivated, engaged, and they have been found to have a higher overall learning ability. This type of experience has a direct impact on the Business Education students' academic performance in their test scores. Thus, it is safe to suggest according to Lutoff (2021) that the learning environment plays a significant role in students' success in institutions.

According to Huffaker (2020), instructional materials support learning content, allow students to engage in the application of the concept and provide an opportunity for evaluation. In addition, instructional materials are developed to facilitate learner understanding. The study by Alabere (2017) as cited by Irumba (2024) revealed that the performance of the secondary school students not taught with the use of teaching materials was very poor. It indicated that it is important that teaching in Business Education should employ the relevant instructional materials. Bukoye (2019) identified the role played by instructional materials in teaching-learning activities. She found that where they are deployed in a classroom situation, it enhances the memory level of the students; facilitates the teaching-learning process; improves students rate of accumulation; serves as tools used by the teachers to correct the wrong impression and illustrate things that learners cannot forget easily; assists in giving the sense of reality to the body of knowledge under discussions; it gives lesson a personal look and encourages teachers creativity and that it permits the students and teachers to experience in concrete terms the learning activities that can promote the idea of self-evaluation.

Instructional materials are resources used to support teaching and learning. However, instructional materials available for teaching and learning business education include the following: printed materials, these include textbooks, workbooks, manuals; digital resources which include e-books, online courses, educational websites; multimedia, which include videos, podcasts, audio recordings, interactive multimedia content, interactive tools such as simulations, games, quizzes and real-world examples, case studies such as real-life business scenarios for analysis, discussion and applications also, assessment tools such as quizzes, tests, and evaluation instruments. These resources help students develop practical business skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Again, instructional materials include; textbooks, blackboards, whiteboards, picture maps, newspapers, audio-visual material, tape recordings, filmstrips, overhead projector, and computer. Others are television, computer kits, etc. The use of each or all of the listed instructional materials simplifies the delivery of instruction and when these materials are put in place it might help to convey information, illustrate concepts and engage learners, ultimately enhancing the learning experience. Hence, it is advised that the business education instructor should have access to the material most relevant to the topic to be taught during the Business Education class. This is because, instructional materials provide the core information that students will experience, learn and apply during a course. Kang et al (2015) observed that any of the listed items hold the power to either engage or de-motivate students. It means that the class teacher will demonstrate knowledge and skill in the application of the instructional material in such a way that it will benefit the learner and increase their academic performance. Teachers of all categories, that is, male and female teachers are responsible in promoting enhanced academic performance of their students, even when students – male and female are known to learn differently under the guidance of a teacher. Thus, the impact of the type of teacher, students learn from could influence their performance. Hence, the performance of male and female students in school subject is one of the growing concerns in the school system.

Instructional resources are integral component for schools at all levels of education anywhere in the world, including Nigeria. The capacity to function effectively in any tertiary institution depends to a large extent on the availability and judicious utilization of instructional resources in the teaching/learning process. Nwankwo, Nwogbo, Okorji and Egboka (2015) as cited by Kigenyi et al (2017) opined that instructional resources are very important for the achievement of tertiary educational goals and objectives through the graduates from the institutions. There is need for prudent utilization of resources to ensure that the educational objectives are met within specified framework. According to Kintu and Zhu (2016), resources are all the things available for an individual, a group of individuals, an organization, institution, association and any combination thereof, to be used for the purpose of teaching and learning with a view to achieving pre-determined aims and objectives, and in this case, enhanced academic performance of the Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

The teaching of Business Education courses in tertiary institution needs to be properly handled. The instructional resources or materials used by lecturers to instruct and drive home their learning objectives at the tertiary level of our education system is undeniably an important issue in practical classroom interaction and successful transfer of knowledge from the lecturers to the learners. Instructional or educational resources assist lecturers to make their lessons explicit and precise to learners. They are also

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used to transmit information, ideas and notes to learners (Awodun, 2019). Instructional resources in this context encompasses both visuals and audio-visuals such as textbooks, digital resources (e.g. e-books, online courses), multimedia, educational software, simulations, games, real-world example, online platforms pictures, flashcards, posters, charts, tape recorder, radio, video, television, computers among others. These resources serve as supplement to the normal processes of instruction.

Statement of the Problem

Instructional resources make teaching and learning more understandable, meaningful and easy. In spite of the benefits of instructional resources to teaching and learning process, the scarcity of it has hindered to a reasonable extent the efficiency of teaching and learning of Business Education and by extension, students' performance. Despite this, most lecturers, especially of Business Education, still resort to the conventional method of teaching the course without recourse to the learning environment needs and learning styles of students. This is undoubtedly and has not help in improving the performance of students in the course, thus, hampering the benefit inherent in the subject that is geared towards economic sustainability needed at this period of our development with emphasis on practical-oriented teaching and learning. This situation has necessitated this investigation that centered on the influence of learning environment and instructional resources with a view to improving learning outcome.

In the same vein, despite the availability of qualified lecturers and course resource, a significant number of Business Education learners in Delta State tertiary institutions continue to perform below expectation in their courses. This has raised a lot of concern whether the learning environment are influencing their academic performance in these courses in the area under review. Also, the issue of the usage of instructional resources without incorporating students has affected the performance of students in these courses. It has resulted in students being passive and deprived of acquiring enterprising skill that the course represents. Exposure of students to the usage of instructional resources has not been encouraging as most lecturers are still employing the talk and chalk method of teaching. It is against this backdrop that the researcher has decided to find out whether learning environment and instructional resource have influence on academic performance of Business Education students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions.

Research Questions

The following research question are raised in the study

- i. To what extent does physical space influence business education students' academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?
- ii. To what extent does social interactions influence business education students' academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?
- iii. To what extent does digital resources influence business education students' academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?
- iv. To what extent does interactive tools influence business education students' academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?

METHODOLOGY

The study will adopt the descriptive survey design. The study population consists of 908 undergraduate Business Education students in the 2024/2025 academic session from four (4) tertiary institutions with functioning Business Education programme in the State. The sample size of the investigation was 227 undergraduate Business Education students which consisted of approximately 25% of the population selected from the Delta State public tertiary institutions offering the programme. The instrument employed for data collection was questionnaire titled Learning Environment, Instructional Resources and Students Academic Performance Questionnaire (LEIRSAPQ). The test-retest method was used to test the reliability of the instrument where a coefficient result of 0.82 was obtained, making it reliable for this investigation. Data generated were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation statistics.

RESULTS

Research Questions 1

To what extent does physical space influence business education students' academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?

Table 1: Summary of students' responses to extent to which physical space influence business education students' academic performance

S/N	LEARNING ENVIRONMENT: Extent to which physical space influence business education students'	X	SD	REMARK
1.	Seating in my classrooms is comfortable and supportive for long study periods	3.03	0.87	HE

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2.	The lighting in my classroom is adequate and conducive for learning.	3.04	0.92	HE
3.	The learning spaces such as classrooms, library, study areas are generally quiet and free from distractions.	3.12	0.91	HE
4.	The physical layout of the classrooms facilitates active learning and collaboration	2.77	0.92	HE
5.	The classroom size allows for effective interaction with instructors and peers.	3.16	0.83	HE
6.	I have access to reliable technology and internet connectivity in my learning spaces	2.72	1.04	HE
7.	The temperature and ventilation in my classrooms is comfortable.	2.84	0.92	HE
8.	I have sufficient access to necessary learning resources such as computer laboratory facilities, software on campus.	2.69	1.19	HE
9.	Classrooms/school facilities (e.g., library, laboratories, restrooms) are clean and well-maintained.	3.20	0.85	HE
10.	Overcrowding in the classroom affects my concentration.	3.20	0.94	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	2.98	0.94	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1, shows that the mean for all the ten items in the scale are above 2.50. This shows that physical space influence business education students’ academic performance to a high extent as can be seen from the Mean scores which ranged from 2.69 - 3.20 and standard deviation of 0.83 - 1.19. However, the overall mean score of all the items was 2.98 and standard deviation was 0.94. This signifies that, physical space influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent.

Research Questions 2

To what extent does social interactions influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?

Table 2: Summary of students’ responses to extent to which social interactions influence business education students’ academic performance

S/N	LEARNING ENVIRONMENT: Extent to which social interactions influence business education students’ academic performance	X	SD	REMARK
21.	I feel motivated to learn when the classroom environment is conducive and well-maintained.	3.31	0.62	HE
22.	Positive feedback from lecturers on my academic performance motivates me to study harder	3.32	0.62	HE
23.	I am more engaged in learning when I feel a sense of belonging and acceptance among my classmates	3.23	0.77	HE
24.	The relevance of course content to real-world business scenarios significantly boosts my motivation to learn.	3.44	0.51	HE
25.	I feel more motivated to attend classes when the lecturers are enthusiastic and passionate about the subject.	3.35	0.63	HE
26.	The support I receive from lecturers makes me feel more confident in my academic abilities	3.40	0.69	HE
27.	Opportunities for practical application of knowledge (e.g., simulations, case studies) enhance my confidence.	3.36	0.74	HE
28.	Peer collaboration and group activities help me feel more capable of tackling complex assignments	3.20	0.80	HE
29.	A positive and encouraging classroom atmosphere boosts my self-belief in achieving academic goals	3.29	0.78	HE
30.	Opportunities to discuss course materials with peers help clarify my understanding.	3.33	0.68	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.32	0.68	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2025

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Table 2, indicates that the mean for all the ten items in the scale are above 2.50. This shows that social interactions influence business education students’ academic performance to a high extent as can be seen from the Mean scores which ranged from 3.20 - 3.44 and standard deviation of 0.51 - 0.80. Nevertheless, the overall mean score of all the items was 3.32 and standard deviation was 0.68. This shows that, social interactions influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent.

Research Questions 3

To what extent does digital resources influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?

Table 3: Summary of students’ responses to extent to which digital resources influence business education students’ academic performance

S/N	INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES: Extent to which digital resources influence business education students’ academic performance	X	SD	REMARK
41.	My academic performance has improved since I started using digital resources for my studies.	3.12	0.81	HE
42.	Digital resources help me to achieve higher grades in my assignments and exams.	3.40	0.75	HE
43.	I feel more confident in my academic abilities due to the availability of digital resources	3.04	0.87	HE
44.	Access to digital resources reduces my stress related to academic tasks.	3.36	0.69	HE
45.	Digital resources contribute to my overall academic success.	2.93	0.89	HE
46.	Without digital resources, my academic performance would be lower.	3.08	0.94	HE
47.	The quality of my assignments and projects has improved due to digital resources.	3.04	0.87	HE
48.	Digital resources make it easier for me to complete my academic tasks on time.	3.19	0.70	HE
49.	Digital resource facilitate better collaboration with my classmates	3.24	0.81	HE
50.	Digital resources help me to stay updated with current information in my field of study.	3.24	0.76	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	316	0.81	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3, implies that the mean for all the ten items in the scale are above 2.50. This suggests that digital resources influence business education students’ academic performance to a high extent as can be seen from the Mean scores which ranged from 2.93 - 3.40 and standard deviation of 0.69 - 0.94. Conversely, the overall mean score of all the items was 3.16 and standard deviation was 0.81. This specifies that, digital resources influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent.

Research Questions 4

To what extent does interactive tools influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State Tertiary Institutions?

Table 4: Summary of students’ responses to extent to which interactive tools influence business education students’ academic performance

S/N	INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES: Extent to which interactive tools influence business education students’ academic performance	X	SD	REMARK
51.	Interactive tools make learning more engaging and less monotonous.	3.19	0.90	HE
52.	I feel more motivated to participate in lessons/activities when interactive tools are used.	3.20	0.65	HE
53.	Interactive tools help me to actively contribute to class discussions or group work	3.11	0.91	HE
54.	Learning with interactive tools feels more like playing than studying	3.47	0.65	HE
55.	I am focused and attentive when interactive tools are incorporated into learning.	3.32	0.73	HE
56.	Interactive tools make complex topics more approachable and fun to learn.	3.16	0.73	HE

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57.	I can retain information more effectively when I learn with interactive tools	3.43	0.58	HE
58.	Interactive tools provide immediate feedback that helps me correct my mistakes	3.27	0.67	HE
59.	Using interactive simulations helps me visualize and apply theoretical knowledge	3.35	0.56	HE
60.	Collaborating with peers using interactive tools deepens my understanding of subject matter.	3.27	0.61	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.28	0.70	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4, suggests that the mean for all the ten items in the scale are above 2.50. This infers that interactive tools influence business education students’ academic performance to a high extent as can be seen from the Mean scores which ranged from 3.11 - 3.47 and standard deviation of 0.56 - 0.91. Similarly, the overall mean score of all the items was 3.28 and standard deviation was 0.70. This specifies that, interactive tools influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding from research question one showed that physical space influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent. This implied that the seating arrangement, lighting, learning space, classrooms layout, classroom size, internet connectivity, temperature and ventilation of the classroom, access to reliable technology and internet connectivity, clean and well maintained classroom and large classroom space are necessary factors to consider for improving students’ academic performance. This finding is in line with the findings of Baaf (2020) who found that students in senior high schools with pleasant physical environment perform better than where the learning environment is not conducive. Also, the finding is in harmony with that of Fisher and Frey (2020) that physical environment plays a role in student achievement and behavior and can foster a positive outlook that support learning, achievement, and social behavior.

The finding of research question two revealed that social interactions influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent. This showed that conducive and well-maintained classroom, positive feedback from lecturers, sense of belonging and acceptance among peers, relevance of course content to real-world business scenarios, lecturers enthusiasm and passion about the subject, support received from lecturer, practical application of knowledge through simulations, case studies, peer collaboration, group activities and group discussion are essential factors that influence business education students academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions. This finding harmonized that of Chastnyk et al. (2024) who found that interactive forms of cooperation with students play a significant role in the success of the latter (students) influencing the effectiveness of achieving educational goals. Also, the finding corroborate that of Saadu (2023) who affirmed that students learn by observing their peers and teachers, with self-efficacy playing a crucial role in academic success.

The finding of research question three suggested that digital resources influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent. This meant that digital resources assist business education students in writing quality assignments and projects, completing their academic tasks on time, facilitating better collaboration with peers, and providing up-to-date current information. These are relevant factors of digital resource that influence students’ academic performance. This finding is in line with the findings of Tibamwenda and Mutesi (2025) that there was a positive correlation between digital tools usage and academic performance indicators with e-book and digital library resources showing the strongest correlation. Also, the finding agreed with that of Ogunbodede and Oribhabor (2022) who found that there was a significant relationship between digital resource and academic performance of undergraduate students of University of Africa.

The finding of research question four signified that interactive tools influence business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions to a high extent. This implied that Interactive tools make learning more engaging and less monotonous, it make complex topics more approachable and fun to learn, retaining of information is more effectively with the use of interactive tools, interactive simulations assist in visualizing and applying theoretical knowledge, collaborating with peers using interactive tools deepens understanding of subject matter. These are basic aspect of interactive tools that help to influence students’ academic performance. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Nima and Dorji (2025) who found in their study that digital technology tools usage positively influence students learning experience and academic performance.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that learning environment has a moderate positive influence on business education students’ academic performance while instructional resource has a high positive influence on business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions. The study concluded that instructional resource is a better predictor of business education students’ academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions than learning environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendation were made based on the study's findings:

1. Management of Delta State tertiary institutions should ensure that the institutions does not lack instructional resource since it enhance students' academic performance.
2. Business education lecturers should ensure that they make use of instructional material during instructional delivery to bridge the gap between theory and practice.
3. Stakeholders of the tertiary institutions should ensure that they provide a conducive learning environment to business education students' since it influence their academic performance.
4. Business education students should endeavour to make adequate use of instructional resource since it aid their learning and influence their academic performance.

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